

Pauli Matrices Versus A Vector Dot Product/ Square Root Combination Part III

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The 3-vector dot product is frequently used in physics due to the momentum and position vectors (as well as electric and magnetic field vectors etc). The dot product is defined as: $A \cdot B = \sum_{i,j} A(i)B(j) \delta(i,j)$ where $\delta(i,j)$ is the Kronecker delta. The problem with this definition, we argue, is that it is not the product of two terms, but of three, i.e. there is a breaking of symmetry between the LHS and the RHS.. If one wishes to make the dot product a product of four terms, i.e. A and a factor and B and a factor, then one sees there is a two-fold degeneracy because $\delta(i,j)=0$ if i is not equal to j , but $i=j$, then $+1 \cdot +1$ and $(-1) \cdot (-1)$ both yield 1 (which applies to $A=B$).. We suggest that one may formally replace $\delta(i,j)$ with an object, such as a 2x2 matrix, which accounts for these two values $+1, -1$ through its eigenvalues, but at the same time must create the property $\delta(i,j)=0$ for i not equal to j . In other words, these 2x2 matrices must anticommute. This is a more direct way of dealing with the dot product issue than what was presented in Part II. In Part II, we made use of an identity linking the Pauli matrices with the Kronecker delta. Here we argue that the Pauli matrices appear naturally if one wishes to write the Kronecker delta as a product of two square roots. This is what leads to the 2x2 nature of the Pauli matrices due to the $+1, -1$ degeneracy. Given that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ arises from this procedure, we argue that it is linked with symmetry in the vector dot product as one breaks the Kronecker delta into a product of its two square roots which leads to 2x2 matrices due to the degeneracy of $+1/-1$.

Square Roots and Dot Product

The square root of a positive real number bb has two values, $+b$ and $-b$, but one must add the $+/-$ by hand. As argued in Parts I and II, it does not appear naturally. One way to create a positive real number bb is through the vector dot product:

$$B \cdot B = \sum_{i,j} B(i)B(j)\delta(i,j) \quad ((1))$$

The Kronecker delta, $\delta(i,j)$, has two fundamental properties. It is 1 if $i=j$ and 0 otherwise. One may see that in ((1)) the LHS. is written in terms of two objects, B vector and B vector, but the RHS contains three objects, $B(i), B(j)$ and $\delta(i,j)$. Symmetry is broken. We argue for writing $\delta(i,j)$ as the product of two square root values to restore this symmetry

Such an approach automatically leads to the $+/-$ degeneracy for a square root, i.e. even though $\delta(i,j)=1$ if $i=j$, a square root term for $i=j$ may be $+1$ or -1 . This duality should be built-in mathematically and we suggest considering a 2x2 matrix whose eigenvalues explicitly account for $+1$ and -1 . The simplest such matrix is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

The Kronecker delta, however, has a second property, namely that it is 0 if i is not equal to j . In such a case, the 2×2 matrices (each with $+1, -1$ eigenvalues) must anticommute.

The first question we ask is: How does one know that the various 2×2 matrices needed will have $+1, -1$ as eigenvalues? Given that one is taking the square root of the Kronecker delta δ_{ij} , for every $i=j$ value, it has a value of $+1$. The square root then for every $i=j$ value is $+1$ or -1 . Thus any $s(j)$ ($s(j)^T s(j)$ (no sum) = 1 meaning the eigenvalues of $s(j)$ must be $+1$ or -1 .

A second question which arises is: How many 2×2 matrices have the property $s(i)s(i)$ (no sum) = 1 and anticommute?

We first consider the simplest such 2×2 matrix ((2)) which has $+1, -1$ eigenvalues. This must anticommute with each of the other 2×2 matrices i.e.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} a^* & c^* \\ b^* & d^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad ((3))$$

((3)) leads to: $a^* + a = 0$ and $d^* + d = 0$ so a and d are either ± 1 or $\pm i$ or 0 .

Next: $\begin{pmatrix} a^* & c^* \\ b^* & d^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = I$ (identity) ((4))

((4)) yields: $a^*a + c^*c = 1$ $b^*a + d^*c = 0$ $a^*b + c^*d = 0$ $b^*b + d^*d = 0$ ((5))

If $a = \pm 1$ or $\pm i$, then $c = 0$ and similarly if b is ± 1 or $\pm i$ the $d = 0$. This describes matrix ((2)). Otherwise $a = 0$ and $d = 0$ so $c^*c = 1$ and $d^*d = 1$ or $c = \pm 1$ or $\pm i$ and the same for d . These conditions lead to three 2×2 matrices which are not simply multiples of each other:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((6))$$

These three matrices are called the Pauli matrices and so one can break the Kronecker delta δ_{ij} into square root factors in 3 space.

In other words: $B \cdot B$ for a 3-vector may be considered at the product of two generalized numbers (i.e. using 2×2 matrices) with:

$$B \text{ (3 vector)} = s_x b_x + s_y b_y + s_z b_z \quad ((7))$$

where s_x, s_y, s_z are taken to be the three matrices ((6)). In other words, one assigns an x, y, z to the matrices ((6)), any way one wishes it seems, and writes ((7)). ((7)) accounts for the $+1, -1$ degeneracy which occurs when one takes square roots as well as for the orthogonality of x, y, z axes. Mathematically, this solution arises for 3 space, but physically one lives in 3 spatial dimensions, so this result may be applied, for example, to $p \cdot p$, where p is the momentum vector which appears in the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + p \cdot p = -m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). This, in turn, leads to the notion of spin. Thus as mentioned in Parts 1 and Parts 2, nature is associated with a

symmetric treatment of the dot product whereas $\delta(i,j)$ loses information because it is the product of two square root factors which have a +1, -1 degeneracy which does not appear in $\delta(i,j)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although we have discussed the issue of the +/- factor of a square root of a positive real number in Parts I and II, here we show how the Pauli matrices naturally arise when one tries to write the square root of a Kronecker delta, $\delta(i,j)$. We note that a positive real number may be written as: $B(\text{vector}) \cdot B(\text{vector}) = \sum_{i,j} B(i)B(j) \delta(i,j)$. We argue that this expression breaks symmetry as there are two objects on the LHS while there are three on the RHS. We suggest that the Kronecker delta should be split into a product of its square roots, but this leads to a degeneracy because $\delta(i,j)=1$ if $i=j$ so $+1 \cdot (+1)$ or $(-1) \cdot (-1)$ may yield 1. In other words, there is a 2-fold degeneracy in the square root, suggesting a 2x2 matrix with +1,-1 as eigenvalues. The simplest such matrix is $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$. For each i in $\delta(i,j)=1$, one must have a 2x2 matrix such that $s \cdot (\text{transpose}) s = 1$, i.e. each matrix has +1,-1 as eigenvalues. Secondly, the matrices must anticommute because $\delta(i,j)=0$ if i is not equal to j . We show that one may find 3 such 2x2 matrices. These are called Pauli matrices. Then a B vector may be written as a generalized number:: $B_x s_x + B_y s_y + B_z s_z$. It is convenient that the result holds for 3-space because this is the spatial world in which we live. In particular, the above result may be applied to the $p \cdot p$ (p =momentum vector) which appears in the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + p \cdot p = -m^2 c^2$ ($c=1$). This in turn gives rise to the ideas of spin $\frac{1}{2}$. Thus, spin $\frac{1}{2}$ appears because one wishes to impose symmetry on the vector dot product expression, and this means breaking the Kronecker delta into two square root factors which cannot be numbers as there is a 2-fold degeneracy +1/-1 which must appear naturally, not be imposed by hand.